

Implications of Linking the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution with the Central Limit Theorem

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The idea of obtaining the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution from the Central Limit Theorem (due to the form $\exp(-m/2 v^2)$) appears in the literature. In particular, in (1), $\exp(-.5mv^2)$ is obtained by arguing that $v(t \text{ final}) = v(t \text{ initial}) + \delta v_1 + \delta v_2 + \dots$ ((1)) and applying the Central Limit Theorem to this sum.

Here we argue that the Central Limit theorem seems to apply to independent identically distributed variables (a sample average) and that $v(t \text{ initial})$ and δv_i do not have the same distribution (the standard deviation differs even if the mean is 0). As a result, we argue that the Central Limit Theorem cannot be used in this context, it seems.

Secondly, we argue that if the approach of (1) holds, one could use kinetic energy ($t \text{ final}$) = kinetic energy ($t \text{ initial}$) + $\delta e_1 + \delta e_2 \dots$ and argue for $\exp(-e^*e/T)$ which is not the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

Thirdly, we argue that $\exp(-.5mv^2)$ is a nonrelativistic result for $v \ll c$, but ((1)) should hold in a relativistic case, leading to a contradiction. In other words, the Central Limit theorem should not choose Newtonian nonrelativistic mechanics over special relativity.

Finally, we note that if one may use the Central Limit Theorem to derive $\exp(-.5mv^2)$, then this distribution represents a physical cost distribution. In other words, without knowing Newtonian mechanics or special relativity, one may suggest a cost of $.5mv^2$ to create a speed v . (Here we work in one dimension.) The Central Limit Theorem would yield Newtonian mechanics meaning that no other physics would be necessary for describing $v \ll c$ dynamics, but a general sampling theorem, which seems to be unusual.

The Central Limit Theorem

From (2), the definition of the Central Limit Theorem is the following. Given a distribution with mean u_1 and standard deviation s_1 , one may create a sample average:

Sum over i x_i / N where x_i is a variable of the distribution in question. ((2))

If $n \rightarrow$ infinite, the sample means used in $(x \text{ ave} - u_1)/\sqrt{n}$ form a Gaussian distribution with average 0 and standard deviation s_1 .

The central limit theorem seems to pertain to sample means (with many elements used to create such a sample mean). The key point we wish to make is that if one is creating a sample mean, then all x_i values must have the exactly the same distribution.

In (1), it is argued that one may apply the Central Limit Theorem to:

$v_x(t) = v_x(t=0) + \delta v_1 + \delta v_2 + \dots$ (equation ((5)) of (1)) ((3))

Here, v_x represents the x component of v and it is argued that one may obtain $\exp(-\text{constant } v_x^2)$ for v_x and similar expressions for v_y and v_z .

We suggest that $v_x(t=0)$ and Δv_i do not have the same distribution and so one cannot use the Central Limit Theorem.

Consider v_x as represented by a Gaussian (mean=0 and standard deviation s_1) as suggested in (1). Then: $v_x(t=0)$ is represented by this same Gaussian. Now:

$$\Delta v_1 = v_2 - v_1 \quad ((4))$$

One must find the distribution which applies to $v_2 - v_1$. To do so, let $y = v_2 - v_1$ and use:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dv_1 \exp(-v_1^2/(2s_1^2)) \exp(-(y+v_1)^2/(2s_1^2)) \quad ((5))$$

$$((5)) \text{ leads to a distribution of: } \exp(-yy/(2s_1^2)) \exp(+yy/(s_1^2 * 4)) = \exp(-yy/(4s_1^2)) \quad ((6))$$

$((6))$ is not the same as $\exp(-xx/(2s_1^2))$ (the standard deviations differ) and so $v_x(t=0)$ is not distributed in the same manner as the Δv_i 's and one cannot apply the Central Limit Theorem to $((3))$, we argue.

Two Other Considerations

We further argue that if $((3))$ is linked to the Central Limit Theorem, then one may also write:

$$KE(t) = KE(t=0) + \Delta KE_1 + \Delta KE_2 + \dots \quad ((7))$$

$((7))$ would then lead to the distribution: $\exp(-KE^2/(2s_1^2))$ which contradicts $\exp(-vv/(2s_1^2))$, i.e. is not the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

Finally, we note that the form: $KE = .5mv^2$ only holds for a nonrelativistic situation. From special relativity one has:

$$E = pc + m_0c^2 \quad ((8))$$

In such a case (the general one), one does not have the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, but rather the Maxwell-Jüttner one which is not a Gaussian. $((3))$ still applies to v_x , however, and so one would expect the Maxwell-Boltzmann to still apply based on the Central Limit Theorem arguments of (1). Thus, there seems to be a contradiction.

Implications of the Central Limit Theorem

We finally consider the implications of applying the Central Limit Theorem to $((3))$. According to (1) this leads to:

$$\exp(-vv/(2s1s1)) \quad ((9))$$

((9)) is a probability function based on a cost $vv/(2s1s2)$ for creating a v speed (in one dimension). For a uniform distribution, the cost is the same for any v . In other words, the Central Limit Theorem (which does not distinguish between special relativity and nonrelativistic Newtonian mechanics) would seemingly choose Newtonian mechanics and dictate that the work required to accelerate a particle from $v=0$ to v is proportional to vv . We argue that this implies that Newtonian mechanics follows from a statistical sampling theorem instead of from ideas such as action-reaction and $dp/dt=Force$ and this would be unusual as action-reaction and $dp/dt=Force$ have been tested experimentally and don't seem to be linked to a statistics, but are rather deterministic.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that (1) and some other works in the literature seem to derive the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution from the Central Limit Theorem because both lead to a Gaussian form: $\exp(-constant \ vv)$. We argue that the Central Limit theorem applies to sample means, i.e to the average of a set of stochastic variables which have the same distribution and are independent. In (1), $v_x(t) = v_x(t=0) + \delta v_1 + \delta v_2 + \dots$ etc ((B)) and the Central Limit Theorem is applied to this sum. We show that $v_x(t=0)$ and δv_i do not have the same distribution, rather the standard deviation differs. Thus, it seems that one cannot apply the Central Limit Theorem to this sum.

We further note that if one could apply it to the sum for v_x , one could create a similar sum for kinetic energy and this would lead to a distribution to the fourth power of v . There would be two distributions, a Gaussian and an $\exp(-constant * v \text{ power } 4)$ expression which contradict each other. Finally, the vv form only holds in nonrelativistic mechanics and there is no reason why the Central Limit Theorem applied to ((B)) should choose nonrelativistic mechanics or relativistic.

We suggest that if one uses the Central Limit Theorem to obtain $\exp(-constant \ vv)$ from ((B)), then this means that statistics (a sampling theorem) is able to predict the expression for kinetic energy without using $dp/dt=Force$ and action-reaction and we find this unusual because Newtonian mechanics is deterministic and based on experiment and does not seem to be linked to mean sampling.

References

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